

Report

Summarising the main findings of a Global Survey to Advance Ocean Observations

Authors	Said M. Hashim, Artur Palacz, Lina Mtwana Nordlund
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1. Introduction and overview of the survey process

The Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science, henceforth the Blueprint, is a support tool for advancing ocean observations, with a special focus on biology and ecosystems. The Blueprint is developed through a co-creative process to ensure it is user-friendly, inclusive and fit-for-purpose. As part of the co-creative process a survey was undertaken between April 2024 and January 2025 to gather insights from a broad spectrum of ocean observing stakeholders around the world. The survey is one of several measures to ensure that the Blueprint reflects the diverse needs, perspectives, and experiences of those who generate, manage, use, or are impacted by biological and ecosystem ocean observations. The survey aimed to identify key challenges in the current biological and ecosystem ocean observing landscape, highlight the existing gaps in coordination, coverage, usability, and consideration of stakeholders' needs that could guide the design of the Blueprint.

To gather the perspectives of diverse stakeholders on the prevailing ocean observation status around the globe, a self-administered semi-structured online questionnaire was utilized. The first section was designed to collect respondents' demographic information, including their consent, names, contact addresses, sectors, years of experience, domain, ocean basin, and professional activities. The second section utilized a 5-point Likert scale. Based on statements related to various ocean observation themes, the respondent indicated their level of agreement on a 5-point Likert Scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The respondents also had an option of selecting 'I don't know' to identify knowledge gaps in the current ocean observing system. Question triangulation was used to gauge the consistency of responses. Questions related to the same theme were randomly spread throughout the questionnaire. The last section of the questionnaire contained closed and open-ended questions to gather more information regarding threats to marine life, Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) familiarity, model examples, and other comments. The survey questionnaire can be accessed through the following DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15528521>

The survey was conducted online to reach a wider audience. The survey was launched in April 2024 and remained open throughout the year, closing on 15th January 2025. Introduction of the survey to prospective respondents was done through marine-related in-person meetings including the UN Ocean Decade Conference in Barcelona, Spain (April 2024), the 7th International Marine Conservation Congress (IMCC7) held in South Africa (October 2024), the EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region Annual Forum 2024 held in Gotland, Sweden (October 2024), and EU Marine Biodiversity Monitoring 2nd Workshop, Sitges, Spain (November 2024). Communication regarding the survey was also distributed via global mailing lists, such as, the Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON) and the UN Ocean Decade Marine Life programme mailing lists, and the BioEcoOcean website.

2. Diverse participation and geographical spread

The survey gathered 92 responses from professionals in 41 countries, including Small Island Developing States (SIDS). Respondents were active in various sectors—science, education, government, NGOs, management, policymakers, intergovernmental agencies, and the private sector—with most having extensive experience in coastal and offshore environments. This diversity underscores the broad perspectives essential in addressing

ocean observing challenges. The survey responses played a vital role in identifying the gaps that the Blueprint needed to address, provided critical input to the evolution of the Blueprint, helping to ensure that it enhances collaboration, relevance, and long-term sustainability across the entire ocean observing value chain.

3. Key Findings: Perspectives on biology and ecosystems ocean observing

Widespread recognition of knowledge gaps

There was a unanimous agreement among respondents that global assessments and improved understanding of marine life are critical. However, the majority believed that we currently do not have a good understanding of marine life, and existing data are insufficient for effective science-based decision-making.

Barriers to FAIR data implementation

While the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles were overwhelmingly endorsed by the respondents, many respondents pointed to the following challenges in attaining FAIR data principles:

- **Accessibility issues:** Ocean data are often difficult to find or access, and are not made openly available.
- **Metadata gaps:** Insufficient or missing metadata was seen as a key challenge for data reuse.
- **Low awareness:** Respondents reported limited understanding of how to make data openly available, and had mixed perceptions of the drawbacks of data sharing.

Interoperability challenges and opportunities

Most stakeholders agreed that local data can support global assessments and that data diversity is not necessarily a barrier. However, many remained unsure about how easily biology and ecosystem data can be integrated across regions. Familiarity with frameworks like EOVS—critical for harmonizing BioEco data collection, processing, and management—was split, indicating a need for broader outreach and capacity-building.

Lack of co-ordination among stakeholders

A major challenge identified from the responses was the poor coordination among the actors involved in ocean observing. Although respondents recognized the value of incorporating feedback from data users and policymakers, many felt that such feedback is not systematically included when designing ocean observing. This reinforces the need for co-design, co-production, and transdisciplinary collaboration as core principles for developing fit-for-purpose observing systems.

The role of society, culture, and citizen science

There was strong support for integrating social, cultural, and economic information into ocean observing. Citizen science was seen as a valuable tool to improve data coverage and public engagement, particularly in areas lacking institutional presence. However, Indigenous and Traditional Knowledge (ITK) remains largely excluded, despite its recognized value and growing endorsement in global frameworks.

Concerns about data products and model usability

Stakeholders expressed uncertainty about the adequacy and accuracy of current data products. Many were unsure whether the collected data are suitable for developing model products or whether these models and data products are properly validated and accurate. Additionally, there was limited awareness about the levels of uncertainty associated with indicators and predictions.

Ocean information services: Available but underused

Most respondents acknowledged the existence of robust ocean information services. Yet, many found them hard to use. There was a broad consensus that existing technological infrastructure is not being used to its full potential, primarily due to usability and accessibility issues.

4. Implications for action

The results of the global survey reveal critical needs that should be addressed to enhance the impact and usability of ocean observing systems:

- **Improve data accessibility and interoperability** by promoting FAIR principles, standardizing metadata, and investing in user-friendly platforms.
- **Foster co-design, co-production, transdisciplinary collaboration and inclusivity** by engaging diverse stakeholders early in the observation process, including citizen scientists and Indigenous knowledge holders.
- **Strengthen education and capacity-building** around data sharing, model validation, and uncertainty communication.
- **Simplify and harmonize access to ocean services** to increase adoption across user communities.

These stakeholder insights form a foundation for developing actionable, co-produced solutions. A more integrated, equitable, and responsive ocean observing system is not only possible—it is essential for delivering the science and services needed to support global ocean sustainability.